

THE EFFECT OF WORK INTEGRATED LEARNING AS A COMMUNITY ENGAGEMENT INITIATIVE IN HIGHER EDUCATION: STUDENTS MAKING A DIFFERENCE

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Abstract

With the rise of unemployment and poverty in South Africa it becomes pertinent for higher education to develop students who can become change agents and make a difference in communities. This paper explores ways in which students in higher education use work integrated learning (WIL) module as an impetus to become responsible citizens and change agents who plough back their knowledge and skills in communities to improve some of their living conditions. A four-point Likert scale questionnaire was used to gather information about community views on the impact of engagement between them and the university. Focus group discussion was used to gather qualitative data. From a total of 70 students, a sample of 20 students who had enrolled for a work integrated learning (WIL) module as part of a Community Development programme was used. They were interviewed whilst a four-point Likert scale was issued to 20 community members. Qualitative data were systematically arranged and categorised into common themes. Inversely, quantitative data were analysed statistically. The findings indicated the importance of higher education through WIL in entrenching a moral obligation on students to become responsible citizens. This includes the creation of a space for them to put their competencies into practice, which elevated them to a post-conventional stage of principled moral reasoning. The findings further showed a significant change in both students and communities in adopting principles of self-efficacy, which influenced both communities and students to believe in themselves and solve some of the problems together. This study concludes that the higher education curriculum through WIL creates a path of engagement between universities and communities by enabling students to make a difference in the community.

Keywords: Change agent, higher education, students and communities, WIL

1. INTRODUCTION

Although government's role is to provide goods and services to people, communities are still experiencing difficulties which erode their self-belief in taking charge of their situation. This indicates that government alone cannot cover all the needs of communities, which indicates the need for other role players including Higher Education (HE) to take part in helping communities through shared knowledge and skills to improve

their lives. Higher education plays an important role in developing students holistically by capacitating and empowering them with both intellectual virtues and other competencies such as problem solving, critical thinking and reflection to become responsible citizens who can make a difference in communities. At the same time, they are being prepared for their career paths. Despite the role played by community development workers and public servants who bridge the gap between government and citizens in need of services as regulated by the Public Service Act 1994 (Republic of South Africa, 1994), students' engagement with communities in sharing knowledge and skills contribute towards change and development. This means that the obligation to help communities in need is the responsibility of all citizens and different stakeholders. HE thus uses different ways including Work Integrated Learning (WIL) modules to engage with communities to reduce some of the country's socio-economic challenges (Jacob, Sutin, Weidman, and Yeager, 2015). In this instance, students who have enrolled for the WIL module under the wing of the Community Development Programme are provided with the necessary knowledge and competencies that are needed for them to become change agents in bringing awareness to communities about their rights and help with some of their challenges particularly those at grassroots level. Students acquire knowledge and skills that they use to identify community needs and channel some of the needs to different governmental departments. To that effect students engage with communities to make a difference in solving some of their challenges. Activities of engagement amongst others include knowledge sharing on sustainable use of resources, improved ways of conducting their daily schedules, use of technology, the development of flyers to get donors particularly for Non-Governmental Organisations All the endeavours are done to support the aspirations of communities.

Universities are a source of knowledge and skills acquisition which students tap into to capacitate, enrich, and transform their lives. Knowledge and skills acquired are in turn transferred and exchanged within communities as way of ploughing back, to modify practices that do not yield progress. The contribution of WIL in producing students with different competencies plays a huge role in higher education. WIL can set the stage for social change because it does not only command a crucial role in the curriculum design, but it complements the curriculum by developing students who use knowledge objectively to have a holistic view of the world by tapping into the real-world wisdom and modelling appropriate behaviour. Similarly, social change in society may arise because of the need to provide solutions to specific social problems. As a result, students offer their help to communities, motivate them to believe in themselves to find a way in their predicaments by showing leadership and caring which not only make them responsible citizens but also changes some of the community challenges. To that effect, through WIL, students can be prepared for work readiness and community subtleties by transferring theoretical knowledge, skills, and technology via practical implementation by engaging and influencing change in the society where they live (Freudenberg, Brimble & Vyvyan, 2010, 43).

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. The Role of Higher Education (HE)

Since Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) are mandated with the responsibility of improving the life of society so that they enjoy a better quality of life, the expectation is to engage with communities around them (Krčmářová, 2012). Arguably social transformation can be brought about in society in many ways. As posited by Cortese (2003), university curricula need to be designed in a manner that it contributes towards the transformation of a society, including the improvement of communities' socio-economic aspirations in line with sustainable development goals. The White Paper for Post-School Education and Training (Department of Higher Education, 2014) provides the framework for HE to lead in the implementation of transformational goals that directs universities to become engaged entities that contribute to the social justice agenda by disseminating knowledge. Since universities are perceived as sites of, HE, they are expected to drive the social justice agenda by preparing students to share their knowledge and skills with communities to realise change at grassroots levels. This means higher education as an autonomous entity also has a moral obligation to lift communities to a desirable state which correlates with their human worth.

In the same vein, HEIs also have a social responsibility and a commitment to use curricula as an enterprise to stimulate communities to take charge and improve their situation (Hall, Hicks, Lane, and Wood, 2017). Given that the lack of income and resources constrain individuals and cause self-doubt and dependency. The significance of WIL as one of the modules in the curriculum that enable higher education engagement with society becomes relevant. Through WIL modules, higher education students not only gain real world experience, but they engage with communities to promote change through the exchange of knowledge which elevates the latter to a state of sustainability (Daniels, Adonis, Mpofu and Waggie, 2013; Fullerton, 2015).

This suggests that the battle ahead of people is to first believe in themselves, transform themselves by accessing knowledge and taking charge of the situation before seeking help and relying on the government for everything. Similarly, Larsen (2015) is of the opinion that HEIs' mandate is not only teaching, but it has another obligation of creating engagements that contribute towards society's wellbeing.

2.2. The Benefits of WIL

The cardinal feature of WIL lies in the placement of students in professional environments to bring synergy between knowledge acquired at university with practice and culture of the workplace and the real world (Smith & Worsfold, 2015). This means that the aim is to prepare student not only for the demands of the workplace and to be work ready, but also to comprehend the world in general and solve problems. Furthermore, prospective graduates experience in the workplace real world conditions, which allows them to apply what they have learned. Coming across new realities in their quest to adjust and cope with the new world outside the walls of the classroom, the expectation is for students to conduct themselves well and display professional behaviour. This also means that in their engagement with the external world in the performance of daily activities, mutual respect is recognised as one of the factors crucial to building trust and relationships with others. In the process of exchanging knowledge, students bring to the society new ways of doing things which contributes towards effectiveness, efficiency, and improved standards. Having been exposed to technology, students also use the opportunity to sharpen their skills further and put them to the test and learn other skills from the community that adds to their development (Gribble, Dender, Lawrence, Manning & Falkmer, 2014). The implication is that changes in technology can contribute towards transforming certain cultural practices for the betterment of society. The WIL module thus indirectly sets the stage for social change by integrating academic learning with workplace learning to help students to connect and derive greater meaning from different knowledge types (Sattler, Wiggers, & Arnold, 2011; Molomo, 2020). The idea is further supported by Sattler et al. (2013) who hold that WIL through its co- and extracurricular nature can influence change and adaptation to new technologies to enhance social norms (Sattler et al., 2013). Furthermore, student employment prospects are enlarged (Smith, Ferns, and Russell, 2014).

According to Jackson (2013), participation in WIL programmes increases students' prospects of understanding the dynamics of the real world better, including the improvement of generic skills such as interpersonal skills, communication, and teamwork. This means WIL provides an opportunity for universities to form a relationship with communities, not only for the benefit of students to put theory to practice, but to also plough back knowledge and skills for communities to discover their worth and use their potentials to improve their situation. Similarly, WIL in universities of technology appears to be an effective way of enabling students to put theory into practice. This means that WIL is not a mere engagement with the workplace and the outside world (Ferns et al., 2014), but it is a curriculum component which helps to develop and assess students' competencies and ability to practice theory in solving societal challenges. Dewey (1933) indicates that learning is an active process of engagement, sharing and exchange of knowledge through communal activities. This implies that WIL makes it possible for students to engage with the real world and in these instance communities to solve some of the problems. WIL can thus be perceived as a range of involvements which benefits all parties, and thus brings reciprocal benefits to students and to those whom they interact with.

2.3. The Contribution of WIL to the Development of Character

The role of WIL is not only to expose students to the real-world dynamics. It aims to build attributes such as moral leadership, cultural and emotional intelligence, as well as global citizenship that can enhance social equality (Coetzee, Botha, Nienaber & Holtzhausen, 2012, cited in Molomo, 2020). This has the implication to of building character as well as stimulating self-belief amongst people to believe in their power of being able to think and apply inherent capacities to minimise lack through innovative way that can improve their livelihoods. On the other hand, Bandura (1977)'s theory of self-efficacy highlights self-motivation and self as an element which motivates people to believe in themselves and remove barriers that stand in the way of people in unleashing their potentials. The WIL module thud place emphasis on critical thinking and develop students to become leaders and managers who can also initiate change in the real world (Gannon, Rodgrido & Santema, 2016). Attributes such as initiative, self-awareness, ethical skills, stress tolerance, ability to solve conflicts, a sense of responsibility and active citizenry are qualities that employers want to see amongst graduates Mutalemwa, Utouh, & Msuya (2020) and can be perceived as character building elements. This implies that universities through WIL activities are at a better space that can shape and prepare students to

navigate diverse situations and manage their reality productively. Furthermore, WIL opens possibilities for students to gain situated knowledge, skills, and experience (Orrell, 2018).

Besides soft skills that are also developed, Fullan and Scott (2014) add that WIL improves students' deep learning skills such as self-management, to build character, and enhance qualities such as leadership, active citizenry, effective communication, and critical thinking skills. Deep learning qualities are supported by Dewey's theory of logic when re-constructing and applying knowledge in social contexts which also enhances development of intellectual abilities that are needed in analysing and interpreting information in real world scenarios.

2.4. Students Becoming Change Agents

There is a view that citizen participation does not have to follow prescriptive, top-down solutions provided by foreign countries for local problems (Theron and Mchunu, 2016). Rather, the authentic participation of concerned citizens who can identify with local problems to understand them better is required. Akin, Engin, Demir and Calik (2017) indicate that youth participation is important in strengthening democracy. This implies that students should engage in acts of responsibility by exchanging and implementing the knowledge and skills they have acquired. This means that they become change agents who establish capacity building and partnership with communities to co-construct and solve problems together. Also, the Manilla Declaration sounds a call for public participation which places a value on social learning whereby local beneficiaries engage in social contracts where they co-create with others (Akin et al., 2017). This means students are not merely consumers, but they model intellectual independence and contribute towards bringing change to surrounding communities. As local citizens are geared towards seeing change in nearby communities, they use WIL as an impetus to share and co-create with beneficiaries. This further implies that universities through WIL are promoting students to become active citizens who are aware of social, political, economic, realities that communities face. They become change agents who learn and exercise their rights as responsible citizens (Anderson, 2012). In exercising their rights as change agents, students thus assume leadership roles which are also one of the benefits of WIL.

3. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

This paper adopts the combination of Dewey's theory on logical thinking and Bandura's self-efficacy theory. Dewey's theory is a philosophy of learning aimed at exposing students to the dynamics of the real world and to using logic when re-constructing and applying knowledge in social contexts (Dewey, 1938). The implication is students can use the knowledge they have gathered in the classroom by using logic to solve real world problems. Dewey's initiative is also aimed at bringing an end to the separation of the ideas of the world from the ideas of the classroom, by developing a fully educative experience through the real world of work (Dewey, 1938). As a result, WIL is used as a vehicle to engage with the world outside the boundaries of the university to forge partnerships through the exchange knowledge and skills that can bring communities to a transformational stage. Dewey's work also set the stage for constructivist theorists whose philosophy of learning attempts to expose students to the dynamics of the real world. Students are influenced to emulate good standards and acceptable behaviour which transforms them to reconstruct their knowledge and perception to a level of maturity, responsibility and to apply logic in social contexts (Dewey, 1938). Consequently, students become change agents who contribute to change in the society.

Dewey's theory is combined with the Human Agency Social Cognitive Theory and the Self-Efficacy Theory as advocated by Bandura (1986, 2006). The Human Agency Social Cognitive Theory indicates that people are self-developing; they have self-control and are proactive. This suggests that communities which are in need can be more than they are (Theron, 2014). This means that social systems can be changed by people themselves when they take charge. In the same vein, the element of intentionality which influence active decision making is adopted by students in the process of WIL to interact with communities to share knowledge, skills, and ideas which stimulate communities to take charge in changing their situation for the better. Commitment and care, including motivation as articulated by Bandura (2006), are qualities that strengthen the engagement students develop with the community. Students take the action of ploughing back ideas, knowledge, and skills into the community as a form of self-reflective action aiming at making a difference in their lives by capacitating them with knowledge and a mindset of dealing with poverty.

4. AIM OF THE STUDY

The aim was to investigate how higher education uses WIL for the mutual benefit of both students and communities and develops students to be change agents who plough back their knowledge and skills in the

community.

4.1. Research Objectives

- I.To explore the extent to which higher education through WIL makes students agents of change.
- II.To determine the effect of WIL activities on students and communities.

4.2. Research Questions

- I. To what extent does higher education through WIL make students agents of change?
- II. Do WIL activities impact on students and communities?

5. METHODOLOGY

5.1. Research Design

A mixed methods approach was used to collect data. A quantitative non-experimental study to assess the impact of WIL on the phase five communities located in one of the black townships in the Free State province using a self-administered questionnaire was used to collect quantitative data which were analysed statistically. Qualitative data were collected by using a semi-structured interview schedule coded manually into themes (Creswell & Clarke, 2011; Du Plooy et al., 2014).

5.2. Sample and Sampling

Out of a population of 70 students, a sample of 20 male and female students aged between 20 and 23 was interviewed, while a questionnaire was distributed to 20 respondents consisting of community members who had interacted with students.

5.3. Methods

Use was made of a 4-point Likert scale questionnaire and a semi-structured interview schedule to collect data.

5.4. Data Analysis

Data obtained through a self-administered questionnaire were analysed statistically while qualitative data obtained from participants were recorded, transcribed, and analysed systematically from content to codes, patterns and to emerging themes using content analysis (Creswell & Clarke, 2011).

5.5 Findings

The table below shows community members' responses to the questionnaire about the impact of WIL.

Statement Number	1	2	4	5
	Strongly Agree	Agree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
1. Higher education prepares students be responsible citizens. (+)	20 (100) %	0 (0%)	0 (0) %	0 (0) %
2. WIL enables students to share, exchange knowledge and skills. (+)	12 (60) %	2 (20%)	1 (5) %	3 (15) %
3. WIL makes students understand the world better. (+)	10 (50) %	4 (20) %	6 (30) %	0 (0) %
4. Higher education capacitates students with logic to solve problems. (+)	14 (70) %	6 (30) %	0 (0) %	0 (0) %
5. WIL enhances soft skills. (+)	13 (65) %	7 (35) %	0 (0) %	0 (0%)

6. WIL establishes engagement between universities and communities. (+)	20 (100) %	0 (0) %	0 (0) %	0 (0%)
7. Higher education through WIL creates a foundation for growth amongst students. (+)	13 (65) %	3 (15%)	4 (20%)	0 (0%)
8. Higher education through WIL invests in communities and in the world of work (+)	13 (65) %	6 (30%)	1 (5) %	0 (0%)
9. Higher education does not share its resource with communities. (-)	0 (0) %	1 (5%)	0 (0%)	19 (95) %
10. What is taught in higher education does not link with what is found in the outside world. (-)	0 (0) %	0 (0) %	0 (0) %	20 (100) %

Table 1: Distribution of community members' responses to each statement

The table above consists of number of responses listed from 1-10 consisting of positive and negative statements.

(+) Represents positive worded statements.

(-) Represents negative worded statements.

* Numbers are converted to percentages.

5.5.1 Likert scale items provided a quantitative measure of WIL and responses from the questionnaire were as follows:

- + Statement 1: 100% of respondents strongly agreed with the statement that knowledge and skills disseminated by higher education prepares students be responsible citizens.
- +Statement 2: 60% of respondents strongly agreed that WIL enables students to share and exchange their knowledge and skills with communities: 20% agreed, 5% disagreed, whilst 15% strongly disagreed.
- + Statement 3: 50% of respondents strongly agreed that WIL makes students to understand the world better 20% agreed, whilst 30% disagreed.
- + Statement 4: 70% of respondents strongly agreed that higher education capacitates students with reasoning skills to solve problems, 30% agreed.
- + Statement 5: 65% of the respondents strongly agreed that WIL enhances soft skills, whilst 35% agreed.
- + Statement 6: 100% of respondents strongly agreed with the statement that WIL establishes engagement between universities and the outside world.
- + Statement 7: 65% strongly agreed that higher education through WIL creates a foundation for growth amongst students. 15% agreed whilst 20% disagreed.
- + Statement 8: 65% of respondents strongly agreed with the statement that higher education plays a big role in investing in communities and in the world of work. 30% agreed whilst 5% disagreed.
- - Statement 9: 95% of the respondents strongly disagreed that higher education does not share its resources communities whilst 5% agreed.
- -Statement 10: 100% of the respondents strongly disagree that what is taught in higher education does not link with what is found in the outside world.

5.6. Themes That Emerged from the Qualitative Study

The following are some of the excerpts that emerged from qualitative data:

5.6.1. University engagement with communities and development of competencies

This excerpt indicates students' feelings on working with communities, *'Working together and solving some of the problems with communities made me to believe that I am able to work with others and show that writing down their needs and cutting down wants can enable them to use their wages only on important things'*.

Another one said, *'I led the discussion on the reduction of crime by speaking to communities to help one another to report such incidents and this improved my confidence and communication skills'*.

The following quote indicates that the students' engagement with communities was worthwhile, *'My engagement with communities broadened my perspective towards life, it opened my eyes to see beyond the surface and learn how to practice analytical skills before making decisions'*.

5.6.2. Developing change agents

"In engaging and working with community members and exchanging knowledge and skills is a way of ploughing in the society and providing communities with other alternative ways of improving conditions".

One of the participants said, *"Changing others' lives was our objective with my group to plough back to poor communities in opening a motivation session which focus on teaching values through stories we read"*.

'I became an agent of change after I listened to some of community women's emotional issues, and through their permission I organised a psychologist who offered them free advice'.

Another participant said, *'I brought change in my community and ploughed back by helping a group of community members who were struggling to read and write certain words in English once a week for 3 months'*.

A group of students said they identified learners in that community whose uniforms were worn out, and they organised a donation drive whereby 30 learners were able to get shirts, trousers, and shoes, and the initiative made a great difference to the community.

Another student said, *'Working together and solving some of the problems with communities in motivating them to attend ward meetings and communicate their needs to councillors as well as channelling some of their needs to relevant departments made me to believe in myself and also stimulated self-belief in them'*.

5.6.3. The power of higher education and benefits of WIL

The following are some of the responses about the power of higher education.

One of the participants indicated that WIL placement made a difference in his life as he gained certain expertise from those with experience: *'Engaging with communities help me to cope with complexities'*.

Other participants said that what they experienced in working with communities improved their maturity level, thinking, and how to relate to diverse groups.

Others indicated that WIL activities opened their eyes about how socio-economic challenges can be reduced through cooperation and partnership of different stakeholders, while others said that higher education enhances their soft skills and develops them to fit with ease in their future career paths in creating spaces for development through WIL in which they could apply the knowledge and skills they has acquired.

6. DISCUSSIONS

6.1. Development of Competencies and Engagement with Communities

Both positive statements and negative statements of respondents in the qualitative study yielded high percentages about the contribution of WIL in enhancing different attributes and enabling students to become active and responsible citizens. Participants indicated that they learned and gained from real life experiences, and this contributed to improve their performance as they comprehended the relationship between theory and practice. As one respondent said, *'Working together and solving some of the problems with communities made me to believe in myself'*. This links with the self-efficacy quality evident in Bandura's

theory, in that students were enabled to demonstrate inner self-belief that they can do things on their own and help others by sharing ideas and working with others in real life situations and this was made possible through WIL activities. Also highlighted by participants was the idea that WIL contributed to students' growth, maturity, self-awareness, and improved human relations, which enabled them to work with people of different backgrounds and disciplines and help them to overcome some of the barriers (cf. Orrell, 2018). The development of competencies such as interpersonal communication and problem-solving skills was also highlighted. Participants also indicated that in navigating through complexities, their perspectives were broadened as well as their attitudes in terms of looking at the world. To that effect, WIL can be seen as an element in the curriculum which contributes to sharpen certain competencies that students possess. In accord with Dewey (1938), WIL activities contribute towards strengthening and bringing a balance between cognitive, practical knowledge, experience, and competencies. This further impacted on change in society due to the need to use appropriate skills and knowledge to provide solutions to specific social problems (cf. Sattler et al., 2013).

6.2. Agents of Change

The involvement of students in community affairs created through WIL enabled them to become change agents and active and responsible citizens who co-created with a community solution to certain problems. Learning became an active process of engagement, sharing and exchanging knowledge through communal activities. This corroborates with Dewey's (1933) assertion that learning is an active process of engagement wherein knowledge is shared with others through communal activities). In their interactions with communities, students assumed roles of change agents by exchanging knowledge, skills, and complimenting cultural practices with scientific knowledge and technology learned from higher education. Facilitating donation drives, channelling the community needs to relevant units, encouraging them to participate in democratic structures to air their voices, giving them advice on recycling including awareness of the importance of writing down their budgets, and the cutting down of waste from the limited government grants all proved that students are agents of change. Students' actions and initiatives demonstrated their role of bringing change as well as ploughing back their knowledge and skills. This further demonstrated a deepening relationship and engagement between the university and community. Gribble et al. (2014) corroborates the idea that solving problems in partnership with others brings the realisation of teamwork, communication, resilience, and conflict resolution and this benefitted both students and the community.

This creates impetus in forging a relationship of equality and trust which reawakens self-belief and the belief that people can be more than they are. The realisation is that WIL activities also enhance students' values and character. Student demonstrated a sense of care and sensitivity to the needs of others by ploughing back into society and making society rise whilst they themselves progressed. In identifying problems that communities are experiencing, students became change agents. They identified problems, analysed them together and found solutions in a logical manner. Drawing from Anderson's (2012) assertion about responsible citizenry, students exercised their rights and changed the situation of learners for the better in the community where they were placed (Anderson, 2012). Likewise, Akin et al. (2017) also confirm that youth participation is an important strategy towards strengthening democracy. This suggests that students should actively participate in helping to change the situation of those who are in need.

6.3. The Power of Higher Education and Benefits of WIL

The current social, economic, and political climate in South Africa calls demands students to become active citizens who also add their weight to the development of poor communities by initiating projects that contribute positively towards improving the livelihoods of communities. Thus, higher education through WIL should create a relationship between communities, non-profit organisations, and universities of technology to enhance career-oriented education curricula which aligns with industrial and social needs to improve employment prospects (Smith, Ferns, & Russell, 2014). Employment is a social need that reduces poverty and crime in society. Hence, opportunities that were reported as gains for students constituted situated knowledge, skills and experience which enabled students to participate with ease and to become conversant with employability needs resulting in smooth transition from university to career trajectories (cf. Orrell, 2018). It was shown that WIL creates a situation where universities, students and nearby communities interact to share knowledge and skills, but also identify societal needs, that need to be researched and findings be used to solve problems and change the lives of communities for the better as well as enhancing students learning. The findings also elucidate the civic role universities play through WIL activities to bring change to communities and discrediting the myth about universities as ivory towers.

WIL has been shown to be one of the most important modules of the curriculum in higher education in enabling students to plough back to communities their knowledge and skills. The finding was that students were able to apply logic and solve some of the problems with communities which contributed to their personal growth and maturity. The findings also demonstrated the significance of WIL of not only preparing students for the workplace but, highlighted its significance in strengthening partnerships between communities and universities. For students, some of the benefits they gained from WIL placements included the reinforcement of concepts and skills learned in the classroom, obtaining practical work experience in applying them in a real-life situation, and this improving their efficiency. It can be added that WIL has attracted considerable attention as an instrument for enhancing professional practice and developing work-readiness and holistic development in new graduates by enhancing skills outcomes management and problem solving,

7. CONCLUSION

The deduction made is that WIL is an extremely important module in higher education which enables partnerships with communities and enhances students' growth and maturity as they use theory and other competencies in a practical real-world situation. The revelation is that students modelled and executed professional behaviour, ethical practices, communication, teamwork, and leadership to make a difference in the community. Shared knowledge, skills, and ideas during their interaction with the phase five community increased self-belief on both students and the community that they can bring change and solve some of the problems. Higher education through WIL not only exposes students to the outside world and competencies that are needed in the world in general, but it gives them the opportunity to actively participate in public affairs to become change agents and responsible citizens. This means students' horizons are broadened about the social, political, and economic challenges that are facing communities and the world in general. They became aware of their potential and how to optimally use resources at their disposal and take charge to change the situation, improve livelihoods and develop character. This paper contributes to literature about the importance of higher education in developing students to become active and responsible citizens who turns into agents of change by working with communities to solve some of the problems using WIL as an impetus for the advancement of a society.

8. IMPLICATIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The implication for HEIs is to perceive WIL as an important component of the curriculum which enables universities' engagement with the whole society not only workplaces. A deeper understanding of socio-economic challenges facing communities has an impact on students' awareness of socio-economic challenges to become active and responsible citizens. Students in ploughing back their knowledge and skills in the society contributed to the social justice agenda as change agents. WIL is thus recommended in all university programmes because of it creates a space for students to develop both cognitive and human skills. It is thus suggested that WIL be integrated in all the programmes because it does not only enhance students' graduate attributes but, it turns them into agents of change and make universities engaged entities that invest in communities.

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